

ROLE AND PLACE OF GLOBAL ENGLISH IN MODERN WORLD

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7762122>

Abstract: This article discusses the role and place of the English language in the modern world in the era of globalization. It is shown that the English language plays a huge role in the global community. The forecasts concerning the further development of global English.

Key words: language, spread of English, lingua franca, global English.

The importance of the English language in the modern world can be assessed in just one line: English is the international language of communication. More than one and a half billion people on Earth speak English, and how many studies - it is even difficult to calculate. In other words, it is the global language of the entire world community.

With the development of information technology and modern communication systems, the spread of the English language on a global scale is taking place. Currently, it is the main candidate for the role of lingua franca, the language of international communication, which is used in almost all areas of society. The unprecedentedness of this phenomenon can already be judged by the fact that English is spoken everywhere in the world, and they talk about it as a single language of interethnic communication, a language that, following D. Crystal, began to be called global [Cristal D. 2003:212]

In the field of international relations, English is the undisputed leader among the working languages as major political organizations (UN, Association of Southeast Asian Nations, British Commonwealth, Council of Europe, European Union, NATO), and less significant ones (African Hockey Federation, European Air Law Association). International organizations that are only from representatives of Arabic-speaking or Spanish-speaking countries, issue final documents in English, although they may not use it in their work.

An illustrative example is meetings of the European Union, which a large number of countries have the right to use their native language. Due to the lack of qualified translators, for all pairs of languages (more than 100) decided use English as an intermediary language.

It is impossible to overestimate the role of the English language in the global Internet. According to statistics, 75% world mail is written in English, about 80% of information (both private and publicly available), stored on electronic media, recorded in English language. More than 1000 languages are currently

used on the web, most likely that the influence of English will increase as it plays an important role in software.

The language acquires a global status due to the political and economic power of the state, whose people speaks this language.

To use English as the language of international communication and mutual understanding required preservation of the norms of the language, while the spread of English as a second language leads to its fragmentation and the emergence new varieties. On the one side, the number of people studying English is increasing, on the other hand, it is losing its relative importance.

English is currently spoken in 113 territories. Some of its varieties, such as Scottish English and Tok Pisin (official language of Papua New Guinea) are recognized as independent languages.

Thanks to English, widespread interethnic communication, establishing contacts, resolving conflict situations, and just communication is possible.

It is worth remembering, of course, that international English is, however, not the language of immediate native speakers, and many of those who use it in their language practice have never been to English-speaking countries. About 90 countries around the globe have adopted English as a second state language, in many countries its study is mandatory, and if there is an alternative choice, for example, between English and German, 85% choose English.

International life passes under the sign of the English language. It is the official working language of the United Nations. Business negotiations, summits, conferences, congresses - everything is held in English. Global cultural and scientific life is possible only thanks to the English language, as a kind of channel through which the exchange of experience, information, and achievements is possible. The Olympic Games - and they chose the official language - English. Once knowledge of English was a sign of intelligence, an element of luxury. Today it is the first necessity, which no matter what goals you have: free orientation in the Internet space or career growth, which, by the way, is virtually impossible today without knowledge of the English language.

Researchers have no doubt that in the near future English will retain its dominant position in the world.

The situation with the English language in the 21st century is truly unique. Never before had any language received such distribution in such a short time.

English today is an opportunity to connect with the global information flow, an opportunity to become an equal part of the cultural world community.

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